

THE ROLE OF INNOVATIVE PROCESSES AND INVESTMENTS IN INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF CONSTRUCTION SERVICES

Usmanov Ilkhom Achilovich

Professor of Samarkand State Institute of Architecture and Civil Engineering

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Abstract. This article discusses the definition of the effectiveness of construction services, the rational use of limited resources, and the evaluation of the effectiveness or results of a company.

Keywords: construction services, innovations, process, development, result, efficiency, investment, organization.

РОЛЬ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ ПРОЦЕССОВ И ИНВЕСТИЦИЙ В ПОВЫШЕНИИ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ СТРОИТЕЛЬНЫХ УСЛУГ

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается определение эффективности строительных услуг, рациональное использование ограниченных ресурсов, а также оценка эффективности или результатов деятельности компании.

Ключевые слова: строительные услуги, инновации, процесс, развитие, результат, эффективность, инвестиции, организация.

INTRODUCTION

In the development of the innovation process, the lack of economic ties between small innovative entities in construction and large-scale construction in the conduct of scientific research and the application of their results in practice does not allow the effective use of existing scientific discoveries.

Building services organizations need to think differently about efficiency, as this metric reflects overall business performance. That is, the final results of service activities are reflected in profit (income). Currently, the essence and concept of efficiency are interpreted differently. Many authors emphasize efficiency as a relative indicator and recommend that it be determined by the ratio of costs to the obtained (achieved) result.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

It is important to determine the effectiveness of construction services. The efficiency of the construction service is the result achieved through the rational use of limited resources. This is manifested in the growth and development of the quality of services and services.

The effectiveness or result of the company's activities is assessed by: the level of satisfaction of internal consumers (employees of the company) with work in the company; the level of satisfaction of external consumers (consumers, buyers, etc.) with purchased goods or services rendered; is evaluated by the benefits of the enterprise for society, including for the environment, the regional economy, improving the living standards of the population, etc.

That's all We emphasize that efficiency in most cases is understood as a positive difference between the consumption of resources and the result achieved.

Innovative innovation in construction by improving the equipment and technologies necessary for the construction services sector facilitates working conditions and ensures the safety of the labor resources employed in it, and also ensures that the growing needs for material and moral consumption are met.

RESULTS

The conducted studies and analysis of scientific literature show that definitions and classifications that reveal the essence of innovative services in construction are not enough.

Based on the definitions given to the concept of "innovation", the concept of "innovative services" can be defined as follows: "Innovative services are services that are objectively new, that is, they are provided to consumers for the first time and create a new market."

Thus, innovative services in construction can be divided into several forms:

- Services for the creation of innovations. In the future, services related to the creation of innovations are themselves innovation services. This type of service is called intellectual innovative services.
- Innovative use services (services related to the introduction of a new product or new technology). "Pure innovative service". In such cases, it is expressed not only by the service itself, but also by the novelty of consumption created as a result of the service;
- Services that create new markets (services offered in the first market, rather than using innovations). We propose to call this type of service "true innovative services". A characteristic feature of truly innovative construction services is the absence of competitors in the market and the presence of a "unique construction brand".

The life cycle of innovative processes in the field of construction services can be divided into 2 stages .

1- Rice. Life cycle of smart innovative building services

Stage I - the creation of innovation. This stage includes development work and marketing activities in research and development construction and is carried out at the request of the customer or according to the opinion of the researchers.

Stage II - the stage of commercialization of innovation, at which activities related to the implementation of innovation are carried out.

The life cycle of real innovative services consists of the following stages:

Stage I - the creation of real innovative services: the search for new ideas that have unusual, non-traditional features, but do not require the use of innovative products or technologies; mastering the production and commercialization of real innovative construction services: creating a suitable physical and technical environment, providing workers with the necessary qualifications, approbation of construction services;

Stage II - the production of real innovative construction services: introduction, growth, slowdown in growth and decline in production .

2- Rice. Life cycle of innovative building services processes

Since the first years of independence of our republic, attention has been paid to the balanced development of all sectors of the economy. The result of this is evident in the results we have achieved in a historically short period of 30 years. “In 2021, the service and service sector in our country developed at a rapid pace and amounted to 74.5% of its GDP.

The largest share of services falls on transport (30.1% of total services), trade and catering (20.9%), utilities (11.6%), finance, including microcredits (8.5%), and communication and information (6.4%). Services.

We are exploring the challenges of linking industry innovation with the adaptive capacity of the construction services industry. Let us dwell on the general patterns of innovation implementation.

DISCUSSION

As an innovation (innovation) in the provision of construction services, a service product, technology or its individual elements, a new organization for the provision of construction services, etc., which is the result of innovative activity that can satisfy the needs of society, effectively appear on the field in more detail.

There are main ways of introducing innovations, i.e. changes that completely renew the organization of the provision of construction services and services to customers, and partial innovations that improve only some parts of the process of providing construction services. In both forms of innovation, one or another aspect of construction and service activities is improved, the time for rendering construction services is reduced, and additional conveniences are created for customers.

We highlight the main features of innovative processes in construction:

- application of technical and technological methods of labor organization in the provision of technical, new machines, equipment and construction services. Currently, this type of innovation in the field of construction services is understood as an example of the introduction of computer technologies in the process of providing construction services in

order to facilitate work with a large number of clients and develop the process of providing construction services as a whole. in connection with information technology;

- organizational and technological, types of new construction services, more efficient forms of construction services and connection with labor organization standards;
- orientation to the use of methods and forms of management in improving management, internal and external relations of the organization;
- comprehensive, simultaneous coverage of various aspects of construction and service activities.

The need to introduce construction innovations is determined by competition and a number of market requirements. The need for their implementation is also determined by the changing needs and demands of consumers. In some construction companies, the resumption of activities also contributes to the elimination of various conflicting opinions that the construction company team encounters in the course of its activities.

Innovative processes in construction begin at the stage of developing a new idea by an active entrepreneur or building service provider. Later, this idea will be refined in the process of creating a project for its implementation. After that, the innovation process continues in its implementation and application in the practice of the construction service.

CONCLUSIONS

The implementation of innovation in construction should be an objective pattern at all stages of its movement. In some cases, an innovative innovation may work well in one construction company or city, but not in another construction company or city. The wider the scope of innovations in construction, the more difficult it is to predict the result. Therefore, it is somewhat more difficult to plan the results of complex updates. Approved innovations at a particular construction company are easier to implement and easier to predict the results of innovative implementation.

“...Today, the experience of many developed and leading countries in the world economy clearly proves that in order to achieve competitiveness and enter world markets, it is necessary, first of all, to consistently reform the economy, deepen structural reforms and diversification, and create new enterprises and industries. on the basis of high technologies, this can be realized by ensuring the advanced development of production networks, modernizing existing capacities and accelerating the process of technical renewal.”

Therefore, the implementation of services with building materials will directly stimulate the development of various industries in the country. This means that some work will need to be done in the building materials industries where consumer goods are produced. We believe that not all enterprises have resolved the issue of introducing quality management systems and service of building materials and ensuring that products comply with international standards.

It is possible to achieve the rapid development of this area by establishing the production of high-quality, material and financial construction products and the implementation of construction services, determining the optimal solutions for installation work. At the same time, it should be taken into account that the introduction of innovations in construction services has a number of advantages, as well as some disadvantages.

We believe that it would be expedient if innovations in the field of construction services and construction production were carried out on the basis of the sequence of innovations.

The sequence of introducing innovations in the field of improving construction services and construction activities

formation of goals for the introduction of innovation in the field of construction production;
determine what tasks should be set for the manager to achieve this goal;
creation and formation of a database necessary for innovative analysis;
creation and evaluation of subjects of innovative activity and their management scheme;
planning of innovative activity (determination of the estimated price, budgeting, etc.);
preparation of construction services and construction production enterprises for the introduction of innovations (recruitment, purchase of new resources, updating equipment and production technologies, etc.);
the first stage of innovative activity, that is, the analysis and implementation of ways to introduce innovations in a construction and production enterprise;
managing the innovation process and making calculations;
evaluation of results and decision making.

3- Rice. The sequence of introducing innovations in the field of improving construction services and construction activities

Taking into account these factors will create conditions for the qualitative organization of construction services in the future.

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